

Synthesis of Heptazolidine

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Synthesis of heptazolidine, a carbazole alkaloid from *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. has been reported to confirm the structure of the alkaloid.

In the previous paper¹ we reported the details of the structure of heptazolidine^a (1) which was arrived at from the studies of its physical data and degradation reactions. To confirm the structure, the synthesis of the compound was undertaken^a.

The synthesis has been effected by introducing the 2,2-dimethyl- Δ^8 -pyran ring in the 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyltetrahydrocarbazole (2). 3-Hydroxy-4-methoxyaniline, m.p. 125°, was taken as the starting material for building up the ring C of the carbazole nucleus. The diazotised amine (4) on reacting with 2-formyl-5-methylcyclohexanone (3) furnished 5-methylcyclohexanone-1,2-dione-1'-(3'-hydroxy-4-methoxy) phenylhydrazone, $C_{14}H_{18}N_2O_3$ (5), m.p. 180-81°. The hydrazone was indolised with a mixture of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 : 1) resulting in 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-8-oxotetrahydrocarbazole, $C_{14}H_{15}NO_3$ (6), m.p. 152-53°. The oxotetrahydrocarbazole (6) on Wolff-Kishner reduction furnished 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (2) as a gummy product which was filtered through a silica gel column when a homogeneous fraction was isolated.

The synthesis of tetrahydrocarbazole (2) was also effected starting from 3-acetoxy-4-methoxyphenylhydrazine hydrochloride (8), m.p. 350°, prepared through diazotisation of 3-acetoxy-4-methoxyaniline and subsequent reduction with sodium sulphite. Reacting 8 with 4-methylcyclohexanone (7), 4-methylcyclohexane-(3'-acetoxy-4'-methoxy)-1-phenylhydrazone (9) was obtained as semi-solid mass. The hydrazone (9) on indolisation with a mixture of glacial acetic acid furnished 2-acetoxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (10), m.p. 120°. The acetylated tetrahydrocarbazole on deacetylation furnished 2-hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyltetrahydrocarbazole as a gummy product (2).

The product 2 was reacted⁴ with β,β -dimethylacrylyl chloride in presence of $POCl_3$ and $ZnCl_2$ and kept at room temperature for 24 h. On working up the reaction mixture was obtained the chromanone, $C_{19}H_{23}NO_3$ (11), m.p. 160-61°; λ_{max} (ethanol) 228, 282 and 300 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.65, 4.09 and 4.22); ν_{max} 3350 (NH), 1700 (C=O), 1666 and 1590 cm^{-1} (aromatic residue). The chromanone was dehydrogenated with 10% Pd/C when the indolo-chromanone (12), $C_{19}H_{19}NO_3$ was obtained. The indolo chroma-

none (12) was reduced with sodium borohydride at room temperature when the alcohol $C_{19}H_{21}NO_3$

Reagents: i, W-K reduction; ii, deacetylation of (10), $(OH)_2, OH = OHCOCl/POCl_3$; iii, Pd/C; iv, reduction; v, tosylation; vi, dehydrotosylation.

(13), m.p. 165-67°, was obtained. The alcohol was tosylated with *p*-toulene sulphonyl chloride when the tosyl derivative, $C_{26}H_{27}NO_3$ (14), m.p. 135-37°, was obtained, which was dehydrotosylated by refluxing in collidine to yield heptazolidine, $C_{19}H_{19}NO_2$, m.p. 148° found identical with natural heptazolidine.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The samples were dried at 80° over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure before analysis.

3-Hydroxy-4-methoxyaniline (4): Nitroguaiacol acetate on reduction with 5% palladised charcoal (200 mg) in alcohol yielded 3-acetoxy-4-methoxyaniline (1.5 g), which was deacetylated with 5% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution and purified over silica gel column to obtain 3-aminoguaiacol yield (35%), m.p. 125-26°.

5-Methylcyclohexanone-1,2-dione-1'-(3'-hydroxy-4'-methoxy)phenylhydrozone (5): To a solution of 2-formyl-methylcyclohexanone (3 g), 4 in methanol (35 ml) in presence aqueous sodium acetate (5 g) was reacted with a diazotised solution of 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy aniline (2 g) for a period of 45 min. The hydrazone obtained was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 80°)-benzene (1:1) (2 g), m.p. 180-81° (Found: C, 64.30; H, 6.70; N, 10.60. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2O_5$ calcd. C, 64.11; H, 6.92; N, 10.68%); λ_{max} (ethanol) 248 and 330 nm (log ϵ 4.42 and 2.88).

2-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-8-oxotetrahydrocarbazole (6): The hydrazone (5, 2 g) in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid (3:1) (4 ml) was boiled for 2-3 min. The brown residue obtained after work up was purified by chromatography over silica gel (20 g). The eluate from a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene yielded a product which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) (1.5 g), m.p. 152-53° (Found: C, 68.4; H, 6.4; N, 5.9. $C_{14}H_{16}NO_3$ calcd. C, 68.56; H, 6.16; N, 5.71%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 230 and 278 nm (log ϵ 4.51 and 4.56); ν_{max} (nujol) 3350, 3170, 1700, 1616 and 885 cm^{-1} .

2-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (2): 6 (1.2 g) in ethyleneglycol (20 ml) was reduced with hydrazone hydrate (1 g, 99-100%) in potassium hydroxide (0.9 g) under Huang-Minlon and Wolf-Kishner condition by heating at 190° for 1 h and subsequently for ~3 h. After work up and chromatography a brown semi-solid mass was obtained which could not be crystallised.

3-Acetoxy-4-methoxy-phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (8): To a diazotised solution of 3-acetoxy-4-methoxy aniline (5 g) was added ice-cold solution of sodium sulphite (8.0 g) and sodium hydroxide (5 g) in water (30 ml). After 5 min the solution was acidified and after allowing the solution to stand for overnight, it was worked up to obtain 8 (4.0 g), m.p. 350°.

4-Methylcyclohexanone-(3'-acetoxy 4'-methoxy)-phenylhydrazone (9): 4-Methylcyclohexanone (2 g)

was reacted with 8 when a yellowish brown semi-solid product was obtained (2 g); λ_{max} (EtOH) 229, 254 and 296 nm (log ϵ 3.12, 3.48 and 4.02); ν_{max} (nujol) 3130, 3260, 1700 and 1530 cm^{-1} .

Indolisation of the hydrozone: Preparation of 2-acetoxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (10): 9 (2.0 g) was indolised by the above method in a mixture of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid, and after work up yielded a light brown crystalline product (1.6 g), m.p. 120°; λ_{max} 235, 247 and 297 (log ϵ 3.85, 4.52 and 4.74); ν_{max} 3350, 1710, 1610, 1510 and 1540 cm^{-1} .

Deacetylation of (10): 2-Hydroxy-3-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (2): 10 was refluxed in 5% alcoholic solution. On working up by purification over a silica gel column, 2 was isolated as a brown gunny mass identical with the compound (2) obtained by the previous method.

Condensation of the tetrahydrocarbazole with 2,2-dimethylacryl chloride: Formation of the tetrahydroindolochromanone (11): 2 in pyridine (5 ml) was treated with 2,2-dimethylacryl chloride at 3° in presence of $ZnCl_2$ (2 g) and $POCl_3$ (20 ml), and the mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 h. Then reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water and worked up. On purification of the product over silica gel and crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether 11 (1.5 g) was obtained m.p. 160-61°. The homogeneity of the compound was determined by tlc; λ_{max} (EtOH) 228, 282 and 300 nm (log ϵ 4.65, 4.04, 4.22).

Indolochromanone (12): 11 (600 mg) was dehydrogenated in presence of 10% Pd/C (150 mg) in *p*-cymene (3 ml) by heating for 5 h on an oil-bath. The crude product obtained after work up, on crystallisation from benzene-chloroform yielded a yellow compound (450 mg), m.p. 150-51° (Found: C, 73.64; H, 6.30; N, 4.77. $C_{19}H_{19}NO_3$ calcd. C, 73.77; H, 6.19; N, 4.53%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 230, 285 and 300 nm (log ϵ 4.61, 4.10 and 4.22); ν_{max} (nujol) 3350, 1700, 1615 and 1590 cm^{-1} .

Reduction of indolochromanone (12) to alcohol (13): 12 (300 mg) was dissolved in dry methanol (15 ml) and sodium borohydride (50 mg) for a period of 20 h. After the decomposition of borohydride with HCl and work up, a homogeneous solid was obtained which after crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether afforded a colourless crystalline solid (200 mg) m.p. 165-67° (Found: C, 73.00; H, 6.55; N, 4.70. $C_{19}H_{21}NO_3$ calcd. C, 73.29; H, 6.80; N, 4.50%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 236, 265 and 300 nm (log ϵ 4.66, 4.18 and 4.01); ν_{max} 3400, 3200, 1540 and 1595 cm^{-1} .

Tosyl derivative (14) of alcohol (13): 13 (130 mg) in pyridine (1 ml) was reacted with *p*-toulene sulphonyl chloride (70 mg) in pyridine (3 ml). The mixture was kept overnight and poured into crushed ice. The residue was filtered, washed and crystallised from benzene (90 mg), m.p. 135-37°.

Dehydrosylation of 14 : Synthesis of heptazolidine (1) : **14** (80 mg) was dissolved in collidine (3 ml) and heated for 6 h. The reaction mixture on usual work up and crystallisation afforded a compound (50 mg), m.p. 150°, which was found identical with heptazolidine (m.m.p., ir).

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